

Audits, Assurance and Absent Workers: An Early Look at Human Rights Reporting Under the CSRD

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Modern slavery remains embedded in global supply chains, and earlier disclosure laws — notably the UK and Australian Modern Slavery Acts — have been criticised for enabling superficial compliance. The EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD), transposed into Irish law in 2024, introduces mandatory reporting, third-party assurance, prescriptive standards, and a double materiality assessment. This study asks whether these stronger design features close the gap between corporate human rights policies and actual practice. Drawing on 21 Irish sustainability reports and 32 interviews with sustainability managers, supply chain leads and consultants, it evaluates how firms are implementing human rights due diligence under the new regime.

Research Findings

Disclosure quality has improved, but meaningful practice lags behind policy. While 90% of Irish firms had human rights policies, only 14% reported direct engagement with value chain workers, 24% tracked the effectiveness of their actions, and 29% set related targets. Firms rely heavily on audits, supplier questionnaires and "Speak Up" hotlines as proxies for genuine worker voice, with remediation largely interpreted as supplier termination rather than redress for affected workers. Third-party assurance is the strongest driver of internal change, but the double materiality assessment is vulnerable to internal bias, low supply chain awareness, and steering-group scoring deflation.

Policy Implications

The CSRD advances prior disclosure regimes, particularly through assurance requirements and duty-of-conduct elements. However, three design weaknesses warrant attention. First, the double materiality assessment lets firms deprioritise human rights through proxy stakeholders and discretionary scoring reductions — The European Financial Reporting Advisory Group (EFRAG) should clarify acceptable practice for auditors. Second, remediation obligations stop short of victim-centred redress, leaving a gap against the UN Guiding Principles. Third, consultants and major audit firms have become de facto standard-setters, raising concentration concerns. Ireland's forthcoming second National Action Plan on Business and Human Rights should address these gaps domestically rather than await further EU action.

Industry Recommendations

Companies preparing for Wave 2 and Wave 3 CSRD reporting should treat human rights due diligence as substantive practice, not a reporting exercise. Four priorities emerge. First, invest in direct worker engagement — audits and supplier surveys are not a substitute for worker voice. Second, move beyond reactive remediation towards grievance mechanisms designed around affected workers' needs and awareness. Third, build internal supply chain visibility before the double materiality assessment, so that steering groups score human rights risks on evidence rather than assumption. Fourth, treat consultant relationships as capability-building partnerships — using their methodological expertise to develop internal knowledge, rather than outsourcing interpretation of material risks entirely.

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Further Reading:

Skerritt, M., Taylor, L., Vega, A., Azadnia, A. H., Onofrei, G. (2026). Regulatory design, institutional pressures and the coupling of human rights due diligence. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 1 - 19

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National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Renewable Energy, Climate Change & Sustainability

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG):

SDG 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth

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